

EVALUATION OF COWPEA (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp) VARIETIES ON GROWTH AND YIELD INDICES IN SUDAN SAVANNAH ECOLOGICAL ZONE OF NIGERIA

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Field trial was conducted during 2022 wet season at Audu Bako College of Agriculture Dambatta's irrigation research site Thomas in Sudan Savannah zone of Nigeria ($11^{\circ}58'N$, $8^{\circ}25'E$ and 475m above sea level). Dambatta Local Government within Kano State has unimodal seasonal rainfall in a year and the average mean annual rainfall of Dambatta and average mean daily temperature were (752.9 mm), annual temperature ranges between ($26.2 - 31^{\circ}C$), The soil of Dambatta site was sandy loam of pH 6.2, Organic matter content 3.93 gkg^{-1} , total nitrogen 0.98 g kg^{-1} and available phosphorus 16.7 mg kg^{-1} . All agronomic operations were conducted according to the experimental treatments. The experimental design consisted of three different cowpea varieties (V_1 , V_2 and V_3) which were laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with intra and inter row spacing of 25 cm by 75 cm on ridges and replicated three times. The three experimental cowpea seeds used for the trial consisted of two improved cowpea varieties ($V_1 - IT89KD-288$, $V_2 - IT90K-277-2$ and Local variety V_3 (gamagari). Local variety $V_3 -$ (gama-gari) produced significantly the tallest average mean plant height at 6, 8 WAS and at harvest followed by variety $V_2 - IT90K-277-2$, whereas variety $V_1 - IT89KD-288$ had the lowest average mean plant height value compared to the rest. The highest average mean value obtained from variety $V_3 -$ local (gama-gari) led it to acquire the highest number of leaves and branches resulted to significantly highest fodder yield at the expense of grains yield per hectare. $V_2 - IT90K-277-2$ variety having the highest average grain yield value of $1,357.44 \text{ kg / ha}$ followed by variety $V_1 - IT89KD-288$ with an average grain yield of $1,016.56 \text{ kg / ha}$. and local variety $V_3 -$ (gama-gari) had the least average mean yield value of 840.17 respectively. Variety $V_2 - IT90K-277-2$ was significantly different and better than rest of the varieties ($V_1 - IT89KD-288$ and $V_3 -$ local (gama-gari) whereas $V_3 -$ local variety (gama-gari) being the least in terms of number of grains, grains weight per pod, 100 grain weight and grain yield per variety. With references to the above research findings, it is recommended that variety $V_2 - IT90K-277-2$ had obtained a significantly highest average grain yield value of $1,357.44 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ with very good performance and was statistically significant than the rest ($V_1 - IT89KD-288$ and $V_3 -$ local (gama-gari). Therefore, variety $V_2 - IT90K-277-2$ is recommended in the study area and could persistently be adopted for cultivation as it gave the highest grain yield pending to further research findings.

Keys: - Wet season, Cowpea, Varieties, Inter row, Seeds, Grain yield.

INTRODUCTION

COWPEA (*Vigna unguiculata* (L) Walp) production

Cowpea crop is one of the most important widely cultivated food legumes in semi-arid West Africa, where rainfall is scanty and the soil is virtually sandy and relatively infertile (Singh *et al.*, 1997). According to Singh, and Tarawi, 1997 most household of the semi-arid west Africa keep livestock in their houses and also grow cowpea mostly as an intercrop with millet and sorghum. Cowpea grains are consumed as food for human and haulms are fed to livestock as folder. Cowpea plant has an ability to fix atmosphere nitrogen which helps in improving the soil fertility of the area, Cowpea plant has a deep rooting system that improves the soil structure and its drought tolerance ability ensures favorable growth compared to cereals even in relatively dry areas. Cowpea is thus an integral component of crop/livestock faming system in West Africa (Singh, and Tarawi, 1997).

Cowpea is an important nutritional component in human diet as well as in livestock feeds (Singh, *et al.*, 1985). Cowpea crop is among the major staple food `crop in sub-Saharan Africa, especially in the dry savanna regions of west Africa. The seeds are major source of plant's protein and vitamins for human as well as their animals and also a source of income. The young leaves and immature pods are eaten as vegetables (Boukar *et al.* 2010).

Cowpea is among the most important source of dietary protein in the semi-arid region of sub Saharan, it is widely grown as an intercrop in cereal-dominated cropping systems throughout the West and Central African savannah. However, the productivity of cowpea is very low due several biotic and abiotic constraints, among which includes poor soil fertility of the area, insect pest and diseases, unavailability of suitable improved varieties, unavailability of resistant varieties such of Striga, drought, etc. in Sudan and Sahel savanna zones, even though the use of resistant varieties, in combination with appropriate cultural practices, offers the most practical and economic option for the farmers (Singh BB., *et al.*, 2002).

Nigeria is one of the world largest producers of cowpea in Africa. According to national bureau statistics of year 2010 production, 3.1 million tons of cowpea grains were cultivated from 6 million hectares of land mainly under intercropping system by resource poor farmers in northern states but due to unavailability of improved cowpea varieties, its production became relatively low (Singh, B. B., 1999). Nigeria and Niger produce 850,000 and 271,000 tons respectively on annual basis of the world production (Rachie, 1985).

International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA) in collaboration with National Agriculture Research Council (NARC) have developed improved cowpea varieties suitable for production to semi-arid region of sub Saharan resulted to increasing of their productions compared to previous where the average grains yields and renewed interest in cowpea crop in the middle-belt and south western Nigeria became increased (Duke, 1981).

Botanical description of cowpea plant

Cowpea crop is an annual crop, its mode of germination is epigeal and has deep tap root system with many secondary roots in the soil surface, its primary leaves are simple and opposite also other leaves are alternate compound and pinnate with three leaflets (Racmakers, 2001).

Cowpea crop is self-fertilized and more especially in humid region areas because of greater number of insects in this region. The flowers are white to purple in color usually 2 - 3 cm long and are borne in part in short racemes (Recimakers. 2001).

The fruits have elongated pods about 12 – 20 cm depending on exiting cultivating varieties. The Immature pods are green and of varying pigmentation ranging from Pink, Red, or Black with smooth surfaces. A single pod consisted of about 6 - 20 seeds mostly with bean shape in nature, but usually short in proportion to their width. The seed coat of many cultivars comes in a wide range of color-white, grey-red and black (Reamakers, 2001).

Ecological requirement of cowpea plant

Cowpea can be grown under rain fed condition as well as irrigation or residual moisture along river or lake and flood plains during the dry season provided that, the range of minimum and maximum temperatures is between 28 and 30 °C (night and day) during the growing season/s. Cowpea performs well in agro ecological zones where rainfall range is between 500 to 1200 mm / year. However, with development of extra-early and early maturing cowpea varieties, the crop can thrive in Sahel where the rainfall is less than 500 mm / year. It is tolerant of drought and well adapted to sandy and poor soils. All in all, the best yields are obtained in well-drained sandy loam to clay loam soil with pH 6 - 7 (Dugje *et al.*, 2009).

Statement of the research problems

Problems associated with cowpea production vary to some extent with regards to agro-ecological zone / s in question. The production of cowpea in the tropics is constraint by many problems, among which includes poor soil fertility, persistence use of indigenous (local) varieties, un-availability of improved varieties, lack of genuine fertilizer, drought, erratic nature of rainfall and its distribution, e.t.c. (Boukar *et al.*, 2010), According to Moody and Whitney (1974), susceptibility of the current cultivating available varieties to pests and diseases reduces their potential yield.

Justification of the study

Nigeria being one of the developing countries in the world and its populace increases at a geometry status where majority of them depends on plants proteins as a result of higher cost of animals' proteins coupled with wide spread of poverty in the country.

This study is therefore designed to assess the performance of cowpea varieties on growth and yield.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are to:

- Assess the performance of tested cowpea varieties on growth indices in the study area.
- Assess the performance of tested cowpea varieties on some selected yield indices in the study area.
- Identify the variety with best agronomic performances among the tested varieties for adoption in the study area.

Materials and methods

Experimental site

The experiment was conducted during 2022 wet season at Audu Bako College of Agriculture irrigation research site Thomas Dambatta, Kano (11°58'N, 8° 25'E and 475m

above sea level) within the Sudan savanna zone of Nigeria. The average mean annual rainfall of Dambatta and average mean daily temperature were (752.9 mm and 26.2 - 31°C). The soil of Dambatta site was sandy loam of pH 6.2; organic matter content 3.93 g kg⁻¹ and total nitrogen was 0.98 and available phosphorus 16.7 mg kg⁻¹ respectively.

Experimental treatments and design

The field trial was laid out in a randomized completely block design (RCBD) and replicated three times, it consisted of two improved cowpea varieties (V₁ – IT89KD-288 and V₂ – IT90K-277-2) with local control (V₃ - gama-gari) which were planted on ridges with intra and inter row spacing of 25 cm by 75 cm. The field trial was demarcated and pegged into 3 replications with discards of 2 meters between replications and 1.0 meter between plots. The gross plots were made up of 6 ridges × 0.75m × 04m (18m²); net plots were 4 ridges × 0.75m × 04m (12m²) that made of a total experimental area of 17.50 m × 14 m (245 m²).

Data collection

Data were collected on growth and yield indexes per plant at 6 WAS, 8 WAS and at harvest as contained in the following tables.

Statistical analysis of data

Data collected on growth and yield indexes were subjected to analysis of variance with the help of GenStat 17th edition and SNK (Student-Newman-Keuls Test) was used to separate treatments means where 'F' test shows significance difference between the treatments as described by Snedecor and Cochran (1967)

Results and discussions

Table 1: Performance of cowpea varieties on plant heights at different growth stages during 2022 experimental wet-season at ABCOAD irrigation research site Thomas.

Treatment	Plant heights at different growth stages		
	6WAS	8WAS	At harvest
Cowpea varieties			
V ₁ –IT89KD-288	34.16c	51.90c	87.17c
V ₂ –IT90K-277-2	47.44b	74.00b	102.89b
V ₃ –local (gama-gari)	58.44a	86.55a	109.11a
S.E.±	2.14	3.18	5.43
Significance	**	**	**

Means followed by same letter(s) within a column are significantly different at 5% level of significance using DMRT

Plant height (cm)

Significant differences were observed on the performance of varieties on the mean height at 6, 8WAS and at harvest (Table1). There were significant differences between the varieties. At 6 WAS, variety (V₃ – local gama-gari) produced the tallest mean height followed by variety V₂ – IT90K-277-2. However, at 8 WAS and at harvest, variety V₃ – local (gama-gari) produced the tallest mean height value followed by variety V₂ – IT90K-277-2 whereas variety V₁ – IT89KD-288 had the lowest mean value respectively.

Table 2: Performance of cowpea varieties on number of leaves at different growth stages during 2022 experimental wet season at ABCOAD irrigation research site Thomas

Treatment	Number of leaves at different growth stages.		
	6WAS	8WAS	At harvest
Cowpea varieties			
V ₁ –IT89KD-288	38.12c	53.93c	108.37c
V ₂ –IT90K-277-2	64.95b	99.95b	173.61a
V ₃ –local (gama-gari)	66.05a	103.02a	135.34b
S.E.±	2.75	3.23	7.91
Significance**	**	**	

Means followed by same letter(s) within a column are significantly different at 5% level of significance using DMRT

Number of leaves per plant

The effect of varieties on number of Leaves at 6, 8 WAS and at harvest are presented in Table 2. The effect of varieties on number of leaves at 6, 8 WAS and at harvest indicated significantly higher number of leaves among the varieties. Variety V₃ – local (gama-gari) produced the highest mean value followed by variety V₂ – IT90K-277-2 and variety V₁ – IT89KD-288 had significantly lower mean leave value compared with the other varieties.

Table 3: Performance of cowpea varieties on number of branches at different growth stages during 2022 experimental wet season at ABCOAD irrigation research site Thomas.

Treatment	Number of branches at different growth stages		
	6WAS	8WAS	At harvest
Cowpea varieties			
V ₁ – IT89KD-288	3.12c	3.03c	3.37c
V ₂ – IT90K-277-2	4.55b	4.00b	4.77a
V ₃ – local (gama-gari)	5.66a	4.52a	4.14b
S.E.±	0.104	0.119	0.142
Significance	*	*	*

Means followed by same letter(s) within a column are significantly different at 5% level of significance using DMRT.

Number of branches per plant

The effects of variety on number of branches are statistically significant and shown in table 3. At 6 and 8 WAS, varieties V₃ – local (gama-gari) have significantly the highest mean branches values followed by variety V₂ – IT90K-277-2 and variety V₁ – IT89KD-288 had the least branch value among the other varieties. However, at harvest, variety V₂ – IT90K-277-2 had significantly the highest average mean branches value compared to others whereas variety V₁ – IT89KD-288 had the least average mean value with regards to their number of branches.

Table 4: Number of pods plant⁻¹, pod weight plant⁻¹ and pod length as influenced by cowpea varieties at ABCOAD irrigation research site Thomas during 2022 experimental wet Season.

Treatment	No. of pod plant ⁻¹	Pods weight (g)	Pod length
Cowpea varieties			
V ₁ – IT89KD-288	30.62b	15.12b	7.17a
V ₂ – IT90K-277-2	44.17a	21.90a	5.27b
V ₃ – local (gama-gari)	24.37c	13.95c	4.91c
S.E±	1.16	1.02	0.18
Significance	**	**	**

Means followed by same letter(s) within a column are significantly different at 5% level of significance using DMRT.

Number of Pods per plant, pod length and pod weight.

Table 4 shows that, the effect of variety on the number of pods per plant, pod weight and pod length of three cowpea varieties were statistically significant. Statistical significant differences exist on number of pods per plant, pod weight per plant and pod length. Similarly, the three cowpea varieties differ significantly in respect of the three above yield indices at 6, 8 WAS and at harvest.

Table 5: Number of seeds per pod, 100 seed weight and grain weight in kg/ha of cowpea as influenced by cowpea varieties at ABCOAD irrigation research site Thomas during 2022 experimental wet season.

Treatment	No. of seeds pod ⁻¹	100 Seeds weight	Grain yield kg ha ⁻¹
Cowpea Varieties			
V ₁ – IT89KD-288	13.56a	15.90a	1,016.56b
V ₂ – IT90K-277-2	13.85a	16.75b	1,357.44a
V ₃ – local (gama-gari)	10.98b	11.50c	840.17c
S.E±	0.22	2.60	9.45
Significance	**	**	**

Means followed by same letter(s) within a column are significantly different at 5% level of significance using DMRT.

Number of seeds per pod, 100 seed weight in gram and grain yield in kg/ha

Table 5 shows that, there were statistical significant effects of varieties on number of seeds per pod, 100 seed weight per plant and grain yield. The result indicated that, significance effect existed on number of seed per pod, 100 seed weight and grain yield. However, significant differences on grain yield per varieties were recorded in table 5. V₂ – IT90K-277-2 variety having the highest average grain yield value of 1,357.44 kg / ha. followed by V₁ – IT89KD-288 variety with 1,016.56 kg / ha. and V₃ – local (gama-gari) being with the least average mean value of 840.17 kg / ha.

Summary, conclusion and Recommendation

Field trial was conducted during 2022 wet season at Audu Bako College of Agriculture irrigation research site Thomas Dambatta, Kano ($11^{\circ}58'N$, $8^{\circ}25'E$ and 475m above sea level) within the Sudan savanna zone of northern Nigeria to assess the performance of cowpea varieties on growth and yield.

The experiments consisted of two improved cowpea varieties and control (V_1 – IT89KD-288, V_2 – IT90K-277-2 and V_3 - local gama-gari variety) planted on ridges with intra and inter row spacing of 25 cm by 75 cm which were factorially combined and laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Significant differences were observed on the performance of varieties on the mean height at 6, 8WAS and at harvest (Table1).

The effect of varieties on number of leaves at 6, 8 WAS and at harvest indicated significantly higher number of leaves among the varieties

The effects of variety on number of branches are statistically significant and shown in table 3. Statistical significant differences exist on pods' number per plant, pod weight per plant and pod length, whereas, the three cowpea varieties differ significantly in respect of yield indices at 6, 8 WAS and at harvest.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from this study, it could be stated that:-

- V_3 – local cowpea variety (gama-gari) produced the tallest mean plant height at 6, 8 WAS and at harvest followed by variety V_2 – IT90K-277-2 variety, whereas variety V_1 – IT89KD-288 had the lowest mean plant height value which led to higher leave number and branches resulted to significantly higher fodder yield at the expense of grain yield per hectare.
- V_2 – IT90K-277-2 variety having the highest average grain yield value of 1,357.44 kg / ha. followed by V_1 – IT89KD-288 variety with 1,016.56 kg / ha. and V_3 – local (gama-gari) variety with the least average mean value of 840.17. V_2 – IT90K-277-2 variety had a statistical significant difference with variety V_1 – IT89KD-288 and V_3 – local (gama-gari) in term of number of grains, grains weight per pod, 100 grain weight and grain yield.

Recommendation

With references to the above research findings, it is recommended that, V_2 – IT90K-277-2 variety having significantly recorded the highest average grain yield value of 1,357.44 kg ha⁻¹ followed by V_1 – IT89KD-288 variety with a significant average grain yield value of 1,016.56 kg ha⁻¹ whereas V_3 – local cowpea variety (gama-gari) produced the least average grain yield value of 840.17 respectively. Based on the research findings, V_2 – IT90K-277-2 variety was significantly better than the other two varieties (V_1 and V_3) accordingly. It is therefore recommended that, (IT90K-277-2) variety could persistently be adopted for cultivation at the study area as it gave higher grain yield compared to other varieties pending to further research findings.

REFERENCES

- Akinola, J. A. and Davies, J. H. (1979). Effect of sowing dates on forage and seed production of 14 varieties of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walps). Samaru Bulletin No. 395, Pp 79
- Boukar O, Ajeigbe, II.A (2010). Farmers guide to increase productivity legume- cereal cropping system in the savannas of Nigeria from, page 5.
- Dugje.L.Y, Onroigui L.O, Ekeleme, F (2009). Farmers guide to cowpea production in West Africa. Pp 1 - 8
- Duke J A, (1981). Handbook of legumes of world economic importance
- Moody .K. and witney. W. K. (1974). The effect of weed on insect to developing cowpea and soya bean in Nigeria. Page 14-22
- Punetha P, Rao V. K. and Sharma S. K. (2011) Evaluation of different chrysanthemum (*Chrysanthemum morifolium*) genotypes under mid hill conditions of Garhwal Himalaya. *Indian J. Agr. Sci.* **81**: 830 -833
- Rachie.K.O (1985). Grain Legumes of Lowland tropics.Advances in Agronomy.
- Remakers, R.II (2001).Crop production in Tropical Africa. Page 33-317
- Singh, B. B., Asante, S. K, Ajeigbe, H., Mohammed S. G. (1999). General guide for cowpea cultivation and seed production. Sasakawa global 2000 Nigeria Project. Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Singh.B.B. and Emechebe, A M (1997). Breeding for Resistance to Striga and Alectra in cowpea pp303-305.
- Singh BB. Ehlers JD, Sharma B, Freire Filho FR (2002). Recent progress in cowpea breeding. In: Fatokun CA, Tarawali SA, Singh BB, Kormawa PM, Tama M (eds). Proceedings, the World Cowpea Conference 111, Challenges and opportunities for enhancing sustainable cowpea production, Int. Inst. Trop. Agric. (IITA), Ibadan, Nigeria, 4-5 September 2000, pp.22-40
- Singh, S.R. and K.O. Rachie (1985). Eds. Cowpea research, production and utilization. John Wiley and Sons.
- Snedecor, G. W. and Cochran, W.G. 1967. Statistical Method. The IOWA State University Press 6th Edition Ames, IOWA, USA P.593